

Current Issues in Teaching Russian Literature Through the Lens of Intercultural Communication

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Abstract: This article addresses the current challenges in teaching Russian literature through the perspective of intercultural communication. The primary difficulties that instructors face in multicultural classrooms are discussed, including the comprehension of cultural and historical codes, language barriers, translation issues, national identity, and philosophical and religious motifs in Russian literature. The article describes methodological approaches and solutions for overcoming these obstacles, such as providing cultural context, employing comparative analysis, and using multimedia materials. Emphasis is placed on intercultural communication as a tool for gaining a profound understanding of Russian literature, fostering respect for cultural differences, and creating a supportive educational environment.

Keywords: Russian literature, intercultural communication, cultural codes, language barrier, translation challenges, national identity, symbolism, religious motifs, teaching methodology, multicultural audience.

In the context of globalization and increasing cultural integration, teaching Russian literature has become not only an educational but also a culturally enlightening task. Exploring Russian literature through the lens of intercultural communication allows students not only to expand their worldview but also to gain a deeper understanding of the cultural nuances within Russian literature and its connection to global literary heritage.

Introduction

Teaching Russian literature in a multicultural setting presents instructors with the challenge of explaining the cultural and historical codes unique to the Russian people and their importance for understanding world culture. Intercultural communication is the interaction between representatives of different cultures, enabling not only knowledge exchange but also the identification of cultural nuances that affect how texts are perceived. Let's examine the main issues in teaching Russian literature in the context of intercultural communication and suggest possible solutions for overcoming them.

1. The Issue of Cultural and Historical Codes

Russian literature contains many cultural and historical codes that may be unclear to foreign students. Russian writers often refer to historical events, religious traditions, as well as images and symbols familiar to Russian-speaking readers but requiring clarification for individuals from other cultures. For example, works by Leo Tolstoy and Fyodor Dostoevsky include profound analyses of Orthodox culture and spirituality, which may be unfamiliar to students from other backgrounds.

Solution: Instructors should prepare a cultural and historical context for the literature, explaining the religious, social, and political realities of the time. A comparative approach can be useful, for instance, by

drawing parallels between themes and motifs in Russian literature and those in literature from other countries. Assignments that encourage students to research the cultural background of a work can also enhance their understanding of the social and religious meanings within the literature.

2. Language Barrier and Translation Challenges

Translating Russian classic literature often faces difficulties in adequately conveying cultural and linguistic nuances. Russian language features, such as its rich phraseology, emotiveness, and authors' unique styles, may be distorted in translations, making it challenging for foreign students to perceive the full aesthetic value and ideological intent of a work.

Solution: Teachers should focus on analyzing original texts alongside translations, explaining the meaning of complex expressions and lexical features. Additionally, instructors can teach students Russian literary terminology and illustrate phraseological expressions by comparing them with equivalents in the students' native languages. Bilingual editions of works, which allow students to refer to the original text and search for their own translation solutions, can also be beneficial.

3. The Challenge of Perceiving the "Russian Soul" and Philosophical Depth

Russian literature, especially classic works, is known for its philosophical content and psychological analysis, sometimes perceived as "mysterious" or even incomprehensible to foreign students. The concept of the "Russian soul," with its tendency toward reflection and introspection, has cultural roots that are difficult to interpret without understanding the foundational aspects of Russian culture.

Solution: Instructors should explain the "Russian soul" through concepts familiar to students, such as existential philosophy or comparative approaches to national psychology. Classes dedicated to philosophical analysis of the text and examination of key Russian cultural concepts, such as suffering, humility, moral choice, and the search for meaning, can be helpful. Using metaphors and symbols familiar to another culture can also ease understanding.

4. The Issue of Social and Political Context

Russian literature of the 19th and 20th centuries, particularly works by authors like Pushkin, Lermontov, Gogol, and Chekhov, is filled with social and political criticism. Authors often address issues of power, equality, and social justice, which may be unfamiliar to students from other countries. These themes require an explanation of the social structure and political climate of Russia at the time.

Solution: It is essential to provide context for the social and political situation, such as discussing serfdom, reforms, and revolutions, so that students can understand characters' motivations and the general atmosphere of the work. Multimedia resources and documentary films illustrating the social and political situation in Russia during the period can be helpful, as well as analyzing similar issues in the students' home countries to draw parallels.

5. The Challenge of Symbolism and Religious Motifs

Russian literature includes many symbols and religious images that play a crucial role in understanding the text. Symbolism and references to the Bible and other religious texts are often used as techniques to create profound meanings but may be unfamiliar to students from secular or different cultural backgrounds.

Solution: Teachers should explain the symbolism of the works by drawing parallels to the students' culture. For instance, cross symbols or mentions of soul-searching in Dostoevsky's works can be compared with philosophical ideas present in other cultures. Comparative analysis can also be useful for identifying universal symbolic images, such as the symbolism of water, trees, roads, and other archetypes.

6. The Issue of National Identity and Patriotism

Russian literature, particularly from the Romantic and Realist periods, celebrates national identity and patriotism, which are difficult to understand without knowledge of the historical background and the

authors' emotional attachment to their homeland. For students from other countries, these themes may seem overly subjective or emotionally distant.

Solution: Teachers should explain the concept of patriotism in Russian culture, drawing parallels with national themes in other countries' literature. For example, works about love for nature, lyrical pieces about Russian landscapes, or historical memory can be compared to similar works in other cultures, helping students appreciate Russian authors' sentiments.

Conclusion

Teaching Russian literature in a multicultural audience requires instructors to be flexible, knowledgeable, and creative. It is important not only to convey textual knowledge but also to immerse students in the cultural context of the works, develop their empathy, and promote understanding of other cultures. Working on the perception of Russian literature through the lens of intercultural communication helps students identify shared cultural codes, better understand cultural differences, and form a foundation for respect toward another culture.

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